

Effect of sodium dodecyl sulphate micelles on the oxidation of L-methionine by chromium(VI) in perchloric acid medium

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of methionine by chromium(VI) in presence of an anionic surfactant, sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) has been studied under pseudo-first order conditions in perchloric acid medium. It was found that increase in [SDS] causes a decrease in rate indicating that the reaction is inhibited by anionic micelles. The critical micelle concentration (CMC) for SDS has been determined in 0.2 mol dm⁻³ ionic strength in presence of the oxidant by surface tension measurements and found to be 4×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³. Further, the reaction is first order in [chromium(VI)], [methionine] and [H⁺]. Methionine sulphoxide is identified to be the main product of oxidation.

Keywords : Micelles, methionine, chromium(VI).

Micelles are biologically important aggregates that are formed in aqueous solutions by surfactant¹, which are compounds possessing a water-solubilizing moiety (often an ionic group) and a water insoluble portion (a long hydrocarbon chain). Micelles are spherical aggregates of 20–200 molecules, containing hydrocarbon interiors and ionic surfaces. The presence of surface active agent often brings about acceleration of reaction by 10–100 times and in a few cases 10³–10⁴ times. Catalysis or inhibition of chemical reaction in solution is due to binding of the reactants by micelle. Micelles are formed after certain concentration of the detergent is reached, called critical micelle concentration (CMC). There is an abrupt change in physical properties of micellar solutions like conductance, refractive index etc. at and above the CMC and thus a sudden drift in property is used to determine the CMC. The CMC decreases in the presence of multivalent ions or high ionic concentrations.

Recently, in the oxidation of picolinic acid¹, formaldehyde², ethanol and propan-1-ol³, D-glucose⁴, dimethyl sulfoxide⁵ by chromium(VI), it was reported that the anionic micelle, sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) accelerated the reaction whereas in the oxidation of L-sorbose⁶, inhibition was observed.

In continuation of our investigations on the oxidation of L-methionine (Met), one of the sulphur containing optically active essential amino acids, using oxidants like manganese(III), iron(III)-2,2'-bipyridyl⁸, iron(III)-1,10-phenanthroline⁹, bromate¹⁰ and thallium(III)¹¹, it was now proposed to investigate these reactions in hydrophobic

environments by mimicking the conditions existing inside the protein molecules. The hydrophobic environment is necessary for most of the enzymatic reactions to avoid the interference of bulk water present in the physiological fluids.

Fig. 1. Plot of surface tension versus log [SDS] (determination of critical micelle concentration).

Hence, it was proposed to carry out these redox reactions in different micellar media, known to create hydrophobic environments by decreasing the dielectric constant of the medium. These reactions are investigated *in vitro* under mimicked physiological conditions so that these results can be extended to real life systems. Further, so far no attempt has been made to investigate the oxidation of methionine in micellar medium. We, therefore thought of carrying out its oxidation in micellar media using various oxidants, while the

cationic micelle, cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) and the neutral micelle Triton-X does not significantly alter the reaction rates with all these oxidants whereas the anionic surfactant, SDS retards the rate of oxidation of methionine with chromium(vi).

Fig. 2. Plot of $1/(A_{\infty} - A_w)$ versus $1/([SDS] - CMC)$ (determination of binding constant of methionine)

Results and discussion

Known amounts of methionine was allowed to react completely with a known excess of chromium(vi) at 30°C in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid medium in presence of SDS and after 24 h the residual [chromium(vi)] in each case was determined with standard iron(II) solution. The stoichiometry was found to correspond to the equation

The product analysis was carried out by adding 0.4 mol dm⁻³ sodium bicarbonate solution to the reaction mixture (after completion of the reaction) with vigorous stirring followed by dropwise addition of benzoyl chloride solution until

Fig. 3. Effect of [chromium(vi)] on the pseudo-first order rate constant, k

precipitation was completed. The precipitate obtained was identified to be *N*-benzoyl methionine sulphoxide which is a derivative of methionine sulphoxide and it was identified by its melting point¹² (m p. 183°C).

Table 1. Effect of $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$, $[\text{Met}]$, $[\text{SDS}]$, $[\text{H}^+]$ and ionic strength, μ , on the pseudo-first order rate constant, k' , at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$

$[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] \times 10^4$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{Met}] \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{H}^+]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{SDS}] \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	μ (mol dm ⁻³)	$k' \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)
2.0	8.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	9.01
3.0	8.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	9.28
4.0	8.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	9.17
6.0	8.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	9.27
8.0	8.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	9.35
10.0	8.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	9.06
4.0	2.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	2.33
4.0	4.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	4.65
4.0	8.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	9.15
4.0	12.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	13.82
4.0	16.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	18.33
4.0	20.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	23.03
4.0	8.0	0.3	40.0	0.2	2.83
4.0	8.0	0.5	40.0	0.2	4.33
4.0	8.0	0.7	40.0	0.2	6.33
4.0	8.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	9.17
4.0	8.0	1.2	40.0	0.2	11.16
4.0	8.0	1.5	40.0	0.2	13.71
4.0	8.0	1.8	40.0	0.2	16.33
4.0	8.0	1.0	0.00	0.2	14.49
4.0	8.0	1.0	1.00	0.2	14.39
4.0	8.0	1.0	2.00	0.2	14.29
4.0	8.0	1.0	4.00	0.2	13.82
4.0	8.0	1.0	10.0	0.2	12.74
4.0	8.0	1.0	20.0	0.2	11.39
4.0	8.0	1.0	30.0	0.2	10.20
4.0	8.0	1.0	40.0	0.2	9.11
4.0	8.0	1.0	60.0	0.2	7.80
4.0	8.0	1.0	80.0	0.2	6.75

The test for free radicals was carried out by taking methionine, perchloric acid, SDS in a thumbgerg tube and acrylonitrile and chromium(vi) in a bent tube. After evacuating the system the solutions are mixed by tilting the tube. The reaction mixture was kept aside and even after 24 h no precipitate was observed. Chromium(III), one of the products of the reaction was found to have no effect on the reaction rate.

Determination of the critical micelle concentration : The critical micelle concentration (CMC) of SDS has a value of 8.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ in the absence of any added ions¹³, but the value decreases as the ionic strength of the medium increases. It is necessary to ascertain whether SDS has the same value of CMC at $\mu = 0.2$ mol dm⁻³ with respect to sodium perchlorate instead of NaCl and also in the presence of HCrO₄ which is present in the system. Hence CMC at $\mu = 0.2$ mol dm⁻³ with

respect to sodium perchlorate and in the presence of HCrO_4^- is determined by finding out the surface tension of the mixture at different concentrations of SDS using stalagnometry. From the plot of surface tension versus $\log [\text{SDS}]$ (Fig. 1) the CMC under experimental conditions has been found to be $4.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 4 Plot of k' versus $[\text{SDS}]$.

Determination of binding constant of methionine : To determine binding constant of methionine with SDS micelles (at $[\text{H}^+] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\mu = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), spectra of methionine were scanned at different SDS concentrations under the conditions $[\text{SDS}] > [\text{methionine}]$. A suitable wavelength is chosen ($\lambda = 230 \text{ nm}$) and A_m , the absorbance in presence of micelle at various SDS concentration and A_w , the absorbance in the absence of micelle were determined. By using the following equation¹⁴ the binding constant of methionine is calculated,

$$1/A_m - A_w^0 = [1/A_m^0 - A_w^0] (1 + 1/k_b D_n)$$

By plotting $[1/A_m - A_w^0]$ versus $1/D_n$ (Fig. 2) where A_m^0 is limiting absorbance in presence of micelle and D_n is $([\text{SDS}] - [\text{CMC}])$ and from the slope and intercept of this plot, the binding constant of methionine was found to be $81.8 \pm 2.0 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 30°C .

The effect of ionic strength on the rate of the reaction was studied by varying it from 0.1 – 0.7 mol dm^{-3} using sodium perchlorate, keeping the concentrations of all other species in the reaction mixture constant. It was found that ionic strength has negligible effect on the rate of the reaction.

Determination of the order with respect to chromium(vi), were carried out at 30°C varying the concentrations of chromium(vi) from 2.0 to $10.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ keeping the concentration of all other species constant. Plots of \log (absorbance) versus time (Fig. 3) were good straight lines, indicating that the order with respect to chromium(vi) to be unity. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constant, k' obtained

Fig. 5. Plot of $1/k'$ versus $([\text{SDS}] - \text{CMC})$.

at different concentrations of chromium(vi) were found to remain constant thus confirming first order in chromium(vi) (Table 1). To find out the dependence on [methionine], kinetic runs were carried out varying the initial concentration of methionine and keeping the concentrations of all other ions constant. The data presented (Table 1) shows that the pseudo-first order rate constants increase with increase in [methionine] and the order with respect to methionine was found to be one. The effect of $[\text{H}^+]$ on the rate of the reaction was studied keeping the concentrations of all other reactants constant and varying the $[\text{H}^+]$ with perchloric acid over the range 3.0 to $18.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Table 1). It was observed that the rate of the reaction increases with increase in $[\text{H}^+]$ and the order in $[\text{H}^+]$ was observed to be unity. The effect of $[\text{SDS}]$ on the rate of the reaction was studied by keeping the concentrations of all other species constant and varying the $[\text{SDS}]$ over the range of 0.0 to $80.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Table 1). The rate of the reaction was found to decrease with increase in $[\text{SDS}]$ (Fig. 4).

The effect of temperature on the rate of the reaction was studied at four different temperatures ($25, 30, 35$ and 40°C) and the activation parameters of the reaction were computed using the linear least squares method and the values of E_a and ΔS^\ddagger were found to be $61.8 \pm 4.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-107.4 \pm 15.9 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The energy of activation indicates that the reaction is moderately slow. Similarly, negative value of entropy of activation suggests that the activated complex is rigid in nature.

Under the experimental conditions employed in the present investigation ($0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} [\text{H}^+]$) chromic acid exists in the form of HCrO_4^- . Methionine is a sulphur containing amino acid and it possess two pK values, one corresponding to carboxylic acid group ($\text{pK}_1 = 2.0$), the other to amino group ($\text{pK}_2 = 10.0$). In 0.1 mol dm^{-3} perchloric acid medium, it exists

in the form of protonated species $\text{CH}_3\text{SCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\overset{+}{\text{N}}\text{H}_3)\text{-COOH}(\text{HMet})$ to the extent of 91%.

The addition of SDS causes a decrease in the reaction rate, which is due to the strong attraction of the protonated form of methionine, HMet, to the anionic micelles. The following reaction scheme has been proposed in which D_n , HMet and $D_n\text{HMet}$ represent micellar surfactants ($[\text{SDS}] - \text{CMC}$), protonated form of methionine (HMet) and adsorbed substrate respectively.

where $\text{R} = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\overset{+}{\text{N}}\text{H}_3)\text{COO}^-$ and $\text{HRSCH}_3 = \text{CH}_3\text{SCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\overset{+}{\text{N}}\text{H}_3)\text{COOH}$

The above mechanism leads to the rate law

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{HCrO}_4^-]}{dt} = k[\text{X}] = kK[\text{HCrO}_4^-][\text{HMet}] \quad (6)$$

where $[\text{Met}]_t = [\text{HMet}] + [D_n\text{HMet}]$ and since $[D_n] \gg [\text{HMet}]$ (7)

the rate equation becomes

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{kK[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}][\text{Met}]_t}{1 + K_b[D_n]} \quad (8)$$

Eq. (8) can be transformed into the form

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{kK[\text{Met}]} + \frac{K_b[D_n]}{kK[\text{Met}]} \quad (9)$$

Eq. (9) predicts the plot of $1/k'$ versus D_n should be a straight line with a positive intercept on the y-axis. Experimentally observed plot (Fig. 5) is exactly similar to the one predicted from the rate equation thus supporting the proposed mechanism. From the ratio of slope to intercept, the binding constant, K_b is determined and found to be $81.8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ which is in good agreement with a value of $79.0 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ obtained from spectral data. HCrO_4^- being negatively charged will not bind to the negatively charged micelle. Hence, the decrease in reaction rate in presence of SDS is attributed to the binding of the protonated form of methionine with the

surfactant and as a result its concentration decreases in aqueous phase, wherein the oxidation essentially takes place.

Experimental

A 0.2 mol dm^{-3} solution of methionine is prepared afresh by dissolving L-methionine (Sarabhai Merck) in water and its strength is determined by iodometric method¹⁵. A 0.1 mol dm^{-3} solution is prepared from 99.9% chromic acid (E. Merck) by dissolving in water and its strength is checked against standard iron(II) solution.

SDS (Qualigens) has been purified by repeated crystallization from ethanol, air dried and stored over fused calcium chloride. A 0.5 mol dm^{-3} solution of SDS has been prepared by dissolving requisite amount of the pure substance in water. All other reagents used in this investigation are of 'analytical reagent' grade.

The kinetics of the reaction were studied at 30°C in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} perchloric acid medium under the conditions $[\text{H}^+] > [\text{SDS}] > [\text{methionine}] > [\text{chromium(VI)}]$ which is being isolated. The progress of the reaction was followed by measuring the absorbance of chromium(VI) at 350 nm using Milton Roy Spectronic-1201 UV-Visible spectrophotometer with 1 cm silica cells. As no other species except chromium(VI) has any significant absorption at this wavelength under the conditions employed, the absorbance of the solution is taken as a measure of the residual concentration of chromium(VI) at time 't'. Plots of $\log(\text{absorbance})$ versus time are found to be linear even beyond 80% completion of the reaction indicating that the reaction is first order with respect to chromium(VI). The pseudo-first order rate constants calculated from these plots are denoted by k' . The rate constants are found to be reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

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